

Guided-blended collaborative learning in speaking class: Voices of non-native English teachers and students from eastern Indonesia

American Journal of Education and Learning
Vol. 8, No. 1, 88-99, 2023
e-ISSN:2518-6647

Corresponding Author

Ranta Butarbutar¹

Sukardi Weda²

Sahril Nur³

¹English Language Education, Universitas Musamus, Indonesia.

²Email: ranta@unmus.ac.id

³English Language Education, Universitas Negeri Makassar, Indonesia.

⁴Email: sukardi.weda@unm.ac.id

⁵Email: sahrilfbsum@unm.ac.id

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this qualitative study is to explore and address two important questions from ten qualified non-native English teachers and five students who have been actively involved as research participants: (1) how non-native English teachers help students improve their English speaking performance through guided-blended collaborative learning, and (2) how non-native English teachers and students view guided-blended collaborative learning as a way of improving students' English speaking performance. Based on an in-depth interview with five students and an analysis of documents, it is clear that when teachers gave their students both synchronous and asynchronous feedback, the students' speaking skills improved. The data that has been analyzed thematically showed that collaborative learning is successful and should be utilized to teach speaking English as a foreign language, they found, teachers should use the following strategies when teaching GBCL: 1) Mixing synchronous and asynchronous learning; 2) Being guided or controlled by the teachers; 3) Forming groups based on roles; 4) Peer tutoring and evaluation; and 5) Collaborative integrated tasks with technology. In addition, we would like future studies to use real experimental and control class designs to conduct guided blended collaborative learning.

Keywords: Collaborative-learning, Guided-blended, Indonesia, Perception, Role-based, Speaking, Technology.

DOI: 10.55284/ajel.v8i1.890

Citation | Butarbutar, R., Weda, S., & Nur, S. (2023). Guided-blended collaborative learning in speaking class: Voices of non-native English teachers and students from eastern Indonesia. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 8(1), 88–99.

Copyright: © 2023 by the authors. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Funding: This study received no specific financial support.

Competing Interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

History: Received: 12 December 2022/ Revised: 7 February 2023/ Accepted: 22 February 2023/ Published: 10 March 2023

Publisher: Online Science Publishing

Highlights of this paper

- Different ways of teaching and learning English as a foreign language in Indonesia are badly needed to show its importance and benefits.
- The models of teaching English as a foreign language might start with the classroom face-to-face (F2F) model and move to the one currently the focus of our study, the guided-blended collaborative learning (GBCL) model of teaching English.
- Interpersonal behavior, experiences and processes, communication and support, and deep learning are four factors that influence the F2F promotional interaction that results in successful cooperative learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Different ways of teaching and learning English as a foreign language in Indonesia are needed to show its importance. Starting in the classroom face-to-face (F2F) and moving on to the guided-blended collaborative learning (GBCL) model. The GBCL paradigm is a combination of ways to guide or control collaborative learning that happens at the same time and at different times. This model supports Crook (1994) claim that different teaching methods and technological tools can help people work together. He also said that computer programs can make it easier for groups to work together. Therefore, the current study used face-to-face classroom contact, synchronous Zoom meetings, YouTube, and Google Classroom (Butarbutar, 2021, 2021b).

To assist with group formation, group work, presentations, and different types of evaluations, F2F was held at the beginning of the class meeting. Indeed, many academics have studied the F2F collaborative classroom interaction, including (Dzemidzic Kristiansen, Burner, & Johnsen, 2019), who states that there are four factors that influence the F2F promotive interaction that results in successful cooperative learning. These factors include interpersonal behavior, experiences and processes, communication and support, and deep learning. Because of their success, they also pushed teachers and students to work together to obtain well-rounded education. Wang (2020), in another argument, claims that computer-supported collaborative learning can enhance speaking skills. Participation in interactive and social video production activities will improve students' ability to communicate, learn a new language, and think about themselves. Banditvilai (2016) also concluded that blended learning is good because, in theory, it can help meet educational goals. Lessons that are better and more useful both in and out of the classroom can be reviewed.

However, no research has been conducted on how teachers and students interact in guided, blended collaborative learning. Besides, De Hei, Strijbos, Sjoer, and Admiraal (2015) devised a possible collaborative learning model to get students to work more in groups. This makes the current study important and possibly ready to be conducted as soon as possible. The study also answers the call for more research into how blended learning can be used in schools to teach English to people of different ages (Banditvilai, 2016). In a nutshell, the following query shapes our comprehension: (1) What guided blended collaborative learning strategies are teachers using for speaking performances? (2) How do teachers' and students' perceptions of guided-blended collaborative learning as it is being put into practice?

1.1. An Overview Guided-Blended Collaborative Learning

Guided-blended collaborative learning (GBCL) is a type of collaborative learning in which teachers guide or control students both simultaneously and at different times. Conceptually, "collaborative learning" is an umbrella term for a number of ways in which students, students, and teachers work together intellectually. Students usually work in groups of two or more, helping each other find answers, solutions, or meanings or making something. There are many different kinds of collaborative learning activities, but most of them focus on how students explore or use the course material, and not just how the teacher presents or explains it. Collaboration is a big change from

how college classrooms usually work, where the focus is on the teacher or lecturer. In collaborative classrooms, the lecturing, listening, and note-taking processes may not disappear entirely, but they live alongside other processes that are based on students' discussions and active work with the course material. Teachers who use collaborative learning approaches tend to think of themselves less as experts who pass on knowledge to students, and more as experts who create intellectual experiences for students [Goodsell \(1992\)](#) and [Dillenbourg \(1999\)](#).

With the growth of technology, collaborative learning is not simply done face-to-face inside the classroom, but also through mediated computer tools and facilitated by an Internet connection. [Bonk and Graham \(2012\)](#) employed blended learning as a mixed learning method of face-to-face and online learning, which they applied to course material. Similarly, [Thorne \(2003\)](#) defined blended learning as the integration of traditional and online learning. Close to this definition, the current study offers a new model, GBCL, which has identifications such as (1) mixing between synchronous and asynchronous, (2) guided or controlled by the teachers, (3) group-based role formation, (4) peer tutoring and evaluation, and (5) collaborative integrated tasks with technology. A closer look at the GBCL reveals its potential to be applied in teaching speaking performance because it accommodates learning styles, time zones, and place diversity. In addition, it is realistic to connect learners to the world ([Thorne, 2003](#)). [Thornbury \(2016\)](#) justifies the basic principles of teaching speaking performances through blended learning, namely, adaptive learning, which matches learning styles, goals, language complexity, and learning tools.

1.2. Research Method

The present study was designed through an exploratory case study ([Yin, 2003](#); [Yin, 2006](#); [Yin, 2009, 2018](#)), which defines a case study whose purpose is to identify the research questions or procedures to be used in a subsequent research study, which might or might not be a case study. Each case has boundaries that must be identified early in the research process, such as at school, whether this includes classroom behavior and students' teachers. Also, he adds that the case study provides a unique example of real people in a real-life situation, enabling an understanding of how and why and hence a rich and vivid description of events.

1.3. Participants' Profile and Research Setting

The current study focused on students ($N = 5$) at the state's higher education institutions. They have chosen purposefully, namely for the third semester of the English education department. Regarding pre-observation, their speaking proficiency is categorized as low. It is probably caused by the fact that none of them ever used any English at home. Besides, they used bilingualism while communicating with their family and society, namely the Indonesian language and the local language, or *Bahasa Daerah*. For this reason, speaking the local language is crucially important for those who have low confidence in speaking English. Besides, three of them had ever taken an additional English course as an extracurricular from school, and the rest got English lessons just from classroom activities as per the school curriculum. All participants have a mobile phone. However, they have never used it to improve their speaking proficiency. They were primarily used for fun, social media, and gaming. To help the researchers identify students' speaking proficiency, their profiles also confirm that their motivation to learn English is to become an English school lecturer after graduation. In such instances, they are more focused on understanding the grammar correctly. Also, it is not crucial to be fluent in English due to the fact that English is taught in the classroom. Overall, their English proficiency level is below 450 on the Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL). Additionally, 10 licensed or certified English lecturers and teachers will participate in the research (5 females and 5 males). They will get an invitation to a focus group discussion (FGD). In order to enhance students' speaking abilities, researchers thoroughly examine what they have done in terms of joint implementation. The

researchers are interested in understanding more about how far participants' experiences in applied small-group discussions or other forms of collaborative learning go. Further, the study was conducted at the University of Musamus Merauke in the province of South Papua, Indonesia. It is the only state university in the province of South Papua.

1.4. Research Instruments

To collect data qualitatively, the researchers investigated and explored the expected data or information by encountering instruments as follows:

1.5. In-Depth Interview Guidelines

The study employed open-ended interview guidelines to support students' speaking ability investigations and examine research questions to help researchers get in-depth information from students regarding collaborative learning as recommended by [Seidman \(2006\)](#).

1.6. Digital Voice Recorder

The in-depth interview should be recorded; each participant's words are their consciousness). An open-ended interview will be conducted with students purposively using a digital voice recorder device. This recording activity is aimed at helping researchers keep and save all the valuable information from students as the subject of the study as well. Recorded data will help the researchers interpret, analyze, explore, elaborate, and conclude the data ([Stockdale, 2002](#)).

1.7. Field Notes

In qualitative research, field notes are frequently advised as a way to record the necessary contextual data. Field notes make guarantee that rich context endures beyond the initial research team with the expanding usage of data sharing, secondary analysis, and meta-synthesis ([Phillippi & Lauderdale, 2018](#)).

1.8. Documents

Similar to how non-textual empirical data, such as photographs, diagrams, and budgets, is frequently used in qualitative studies, many qualitative studies include the analysis of empirical documents, such as political speeches, patient files, homepages of public and private organizations, and legislation from various fields ([Prior, 2016](#)). For this reason, the researchers used the handout that lecturers and students utilize, as well as the teacher's list evaluation, journal reflection, student's answer sheet, lesson plan, and portfolio. All of the accompanying documentation will be utilized to confirm and justify the improvement of speaking abilities among students during collaborative learning.

1.9. Technique for Collecting Data

The data collection technique in this study was carried out through in-depth interviews, focus group discussion (FGD), taking field notes, and observation.

1.10. In-Depth Interview

[Karabinar and Guler \(2013\)](#) say that in-depth interviews are a useful way to collect qualitative data that can be used for a variety of goals, such as figuring out what people need, making programs better, finding problems, and

planning strategies. In-depth qualitative interviews are important for developing and evaluating extension projects because they use an open-ended, discovery-based style that allows the interviewer to learn a lot about the respondent's feelings and thoughts on the subject (Karabinar & Guler, 2013). The following interview questions were used by the researchers to achieve this goal: "Would you discuss your experiences during GBCL?" "Tell us more about the tactics you used during GBCL, and tell us more about your perspective prior to, during, and after applying GBCL."

1.11. Focus Group Discussion

Kitzinger (2005) explores perceptions, experiences, and understandings through the use of group dynamics. Focus group research is a widely common practice in many academic fields and among professionals, especially in the field of education research. Individual interviews and participant observation aren't the only ways to get data; focus groups also make a great alternative or addition.

1.12. Taking Field Notes

Muswazi and Nhamo (2013) stated that good field notes should be detailed and include portraits of participants' voices, a reconstruction of the conversation, a description of the environment, and specific explanations of what the observer did. The notes should be thoughtful enough to include thoughts about how data are collected and analyzed, ethical problems and conflicts, the observer's point of view, and how theories are made. Include a summary, a thorough bibliography, and the topic. We cannot always be sure that the places we obtained information from in the past, like the Internet, will still be there when we go back to them. Therefore, it is important to provide advice, such as by including bibliographic information. Even if researchers cannot write full field notes right away, they should still give a summary of what happened and any important quotes. In addition, notes were taken during FGD and observation.

1.13. Observation

As a research instrument, the study employed observation to observe and see students' and teachers' behaviors and involvement during guided collaborative learning. It has done so in response to the first research question, as mentioned previously: "What guided blended collaborative learning methodologies are teachers using for speaking performances?" It occurred naturally without interrupting observant, and its results have the potential to help research when doing interpretation and writing up gathered data. Also, data from observation is insightful for supporting in-depth interviewing and field notes, obviously (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015).

1.14. Techniques of Data Analysis

To familiarize themselves with the data analysis, the qualitative results of the in-depth interviews were used for exploratory analysis. Exploratory research is utilized to study issues that are not clearly defined. It is carried out to gain a deeper understanding of the situation at hand, but will not produce any concrete findings. In this type of research, the researchers begin with a broad concept and use it as a tool to pinpoint problems that might serve as the subject of further study. It is crucial for the researchers to be open to altering the course in response to the discovery of fresh information or insight.

1.15. Validity or Trustworthiness

Qualitative analysis may be moving, enlightening, skillful, or incorrect. Despite how well told it is, the tale does not match the statistics. When reasonable coworkers double-checked the case, they arrived at quite different conclusions. Participants in the case did not share the researchers' views. The thought that there is no one reality to accurately describe makes the phenomenologist giggle, but he or she can't help but have the uneasy impression that there are, in fact, logical conclusions somewhere. The very people whose activities concern the participants who provided the initial data should pay attention to the excellent explanation. The approach of soliciting participant input is recommended by [Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña \(2018\)](#).

2. FINDINGS

In response to the first research question, "What guided blended collaborative learning strategies are teachers using for speaking performances?" In light of the teacher's perspective, "I discovered that by implementing the following strategies during GBCL, I was able to encourage students to be more active and to participate in the chosen topic discussion:

2.1. Guided-Blended Collaborative Learning

Four groups of five pupils each were formed based on the perceptions and experiences of the teachers. Two of the 20 students who were present for class that day felt compelled to speak up, while the other 16 remained silent. Teachers assigned topics for group members to discuss during the first meeting, and each group was asked to provide a summary of the discussion at the end of the face-to-face (F2F) class meeting that day.

The teacher modified her teaching methods after the first meeting's review, allowing students to select their own, engaging themes and providing them time to collaborate under the teacher's supervision (e.g., encouraging student passive participation in collaboration). Up to the seventh meeting, this method was consistently employed; at the eighth meeting, the teachers invited each group to share their findings. Teachers for group presentations closely monitored each student who wasn't actively participating, for example by making remarks, ideas, or even a rebuttal. Teachers occasionally mentioned a student by name, as in "grouped into four groups with five members each. Teachers chose subjects for groups to discuss during the initial meeting, and at the conclusion of the class meeting that day, each group was requested to offer a summary of the discussion. Face-to-face (F2F) instruction is used, however according to the teachers' observations, only two of the 20 children present that day felt the need to speak up, and the others chose to remain silent. Regarding the initial evaluation, the teacher adjusted her method of instruction in the second meeting and let the students to select freely their own interesting subjects. They are given time to collaborate under the teacher's supervision (e.g., encouraging passive student participation in collaboration). Up until the eighth meeting, this tactic was continued. Teachers asked each group to report their outcomes at the seventh meeting. Teachers for group presentations were closely monitoring any student who wasn't actively contributing by making comments, recommendations, or even a rebuttal. Teachers occasionally called out a specific student by name, such as "Barbara, speak up; do not keep quiet." The instructors stated that their goal was to motivate and inspire each student to participate more actively in class debates and presentations. Based on the teachers' observations and thoughts at the conclusion of the eighth meeting, instructors and students decided to continue class meetings through Zoom meetings (synchronous) from the ninth meeting until the end, with group projects being submitted through Google Classroom (asynchronous). To keep the learning environment interesting and engaging, this strategy was updated. For the project, each group created a role-playing interview in which one member acted as the interviewer and the others as the interviewee. Every one of their teamwork efforts was

captured on camera, and the final output was uploaded to Google Classroom. Everyone was tasked with watching the group video production and providing constructive criticism. The study's classification of the students' findings was as Figure 1 follows:

Figure 1. Guided-blended collaborative learning results.

2.2. Role-Based Group Formation

Students' speaking performance affected how active their theories were during group projects. However, their activity did not go as well as the teacher anticipated. According to the findings of the current study, teachers divided students into groups based on their responsibilities.

Figure 2. Role-based group formation.

Based on the students' duties within each group, the groups were formed as shown in Figure 2. On the subject that the teachers had chosen, they worked together. Each student participates in and assumes responsibility for their roles. such as leadership positions to oversee all group operations from the beginning to the end of collaboration. When teachers requested students to begin group presentations, both face-to-face in front of the class and via Zoom, those who had speaking and presenting duties spoke up. "I contrasted the establishment of student groups generally with the formation of role-based groups, and it is significant in increasing their level of activity." In my opinion, this is because each student is responsible for their assigned responsibilities; thus, the more my student role is assigned, the more actively I speak. (Student 1: January 13, 2023).

2.3. Collaboration with Technology Integration

Students are more engaged in speaking performance when task-based technology is provided to them. They were inspired and encouraged by technology to speak up more forcefully and fearlessly. According to the study, the Say It: The English Pronunciation App enhanced student pronunciation when speaking performance. Each group was assisted by the teacher in selecting an engaging topic and the presentation was videotaped. The Say It: English

Pronunciation app was used by each group member to verify their correct pronunciation before being uploaded to YouTube and Google Classroom. Due to its ease of access, this program dramatically enhanced students' pronunciation. "In my view, collaborative learning that incorporates technology is the best course of action given the situation my pupils are in." (January 13, 2023: Teacher 2)

2.4. Peer Evaluation is Empowering for Speaking Performances

The teacher believes that peer evaluation is one method for ensuring the effectiveness of synchronous and asynchronous collaborative learning. When the students gave presentations in groups, their classmates evaluated them verbally and in writing. After repeating or rephrasing their mistakes, peers who used these tactics were more likely to talk clearly. Peers served as scaffolds as a result. It is clarified by the following little excerpt: "I asked all of my pupils to review and offer them a constructive suggestion to enable me to give a measured and fair evaluation." Regarding peer review, for pupils to perform better in the meetings that follow (Teacher, January 15, 2023). Peers were also a level below student group members, so the method created a more relaxed and stress-free environment in the classroom. Peer review was successful in fixing my error since it motivated me to participate actively in the group discussion rather than criticizing it. "My pronunciation has improved as my group MKO repeatedly practiced the right pronunciation before I attempted to do so" (Student 4, January 6, 2022).

Table 1. Teachers' perception of GBCL implementation.

Teachers' perception in terms of	Always done	Sometimes	Not at all
1. Preparation Planned well before filling classroom activities	Yes	No	No
2. Structures of lesson Systematically checked for students' understanding	Yes	No	No
3. Instructional performances Students participation motivation	Yes	No	No
4. Teaching tools Use self-design lesson plans & course materials	No	No	No
5. Teaching materials Use printed and electronic learning sources	Yes	No	No
6. Teaching method Round table discussion, debate, presentation	No	Yes	No
7. Engagement Academic, emotional, behavioral	Yes	No	No
8. Classroom management Round students seat periodically	No	Yes	No
9. Documentation Teacher use a list of evaluation	Yes	No	No
10. Evaluation Daily teacher and peer evaluation	No	Yes	No

The second study question was, "How do teachers and students perceive guided-blended collaborative learning while it is being implemented?" When GBCL is applied to speaking performances, it is not only supervised or monitored regularly by the teachers but also provided extra time for rehearsing, according to focus group discussion results and papers utilized by teachers for analysis. Students' speech becomes more fluid as they practice. In essence, GBCL can be beneficial for enhancing speaking performance when the following elements are used, as shown in Table 1, according to teachers' and students' perspectives.

3. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to look into two things: (1) how teachers help students improve their speaking performance in guided blended collaborative learning, and (2) how teachers and students see guided blended

collaborative learning. Based on an in-depth interview with five students and evidence from document analysis, it was shown that when teachers gave their students synchronous and asynchronous guidance, the students' speaking performance improved. Ten qualified teachers participated in the FGD sharing session. According to what it found, teachers should use the following strategies when teaching GBCL: (1) mixing between synchronous and asynchronous, (2) guided or controlled by the teachers, (3) group-based role formation, (4) peer tutoring and evaluation, and (5) collaborative integrated tasks with technology. This finding was supported by in-depth interviews with the teachers and students. The students' speaking skills also got better, which was confirmed by the FGD sharing session, field notes, and document analysis.

In addition, an expanding document analysis showed that students' ratings of the formative evaluation showed that pronunciation, fluency, and accuracy all got better when students worked together to use technology. These results are the same as those of other researchers, like [Lin \(2015\)](#) who wrote about computer-supported collaborative learning in language learning. [Thornbury \(2016\)](#), who supported the fundamental ideas of teaching speaking performances through blended learning, confirmed the benefits of GBCL on students' better speaking performance. He asserted that blended learning is an adaptable and suitable learning method. In this way, the current study agrees with Thornbury's conclusion, because even though teachers let students choose the topic of conversation, students still dominated and were passive during face-to-face speaking activities. Collaboration only works for the group's speaker and leader, while the other members sometimes contribute. Some students, on the other hand, save their speaking abilities until they are required or pushed. Fortunately, group members became more involved once the teachers blended classroom discussions through a virtual zoom meeting. Additionally, students reported that after taking part in zoom sessions, they felt less pressure and had more confidence in their previous group presentations. In this instance, the traditional F2F classroom setting occasionally made children feel under pressure and reluctant to speak up out of fear of mispronouncing words ([Tauchid, Saleh, Hartono, & Mujiyanto, 2022](#)). As they obtained deeper comprehension, students' speaking skills and word pronunciation improved. The lists of grades reviewed, which were well documented by teachers, served as proof.

Furthermore, the observations confirmed that the GBCL was successful in assisting students in performing and mastering presentation styles. It was recognized that instructors led and directed pupils in group-speaking exercises. According to our observational findings and recorded notes, collaborative learning with the teachers in charge was generally distinct from collaborative learning. In this vein, our study found that students were more engaged and performed better when teachers guided and regulated their collaborative speaking. According to [Liang \(2022\)](#), teachers thought it premature in terms of students' self-awareness, willingness to speak up, and understanding of what collaboration meant. She noticed that interactions among pupils helped lessen their hesitation in communicating. Students were more prone to speak up with confidence as they interacted with their peers and the class as a whole. In contrast, [Nur and Butarbutar \(2022a\)](#); [Nur and Butarbutar \(2022b\)](#) asserted that through self-directed learning, YouTube channels have the ability to enhance students' speaking abilities ([Butarbutar, 2021](#); [Butarbutar & Leba, 2023](#)).

Students' speaking skills greatly increase when synchronous and asynchronous education are combined with teachers. These blended learning strategies are suitable to meet the learning preferences of Indonesian EFL students. As a result, half of the 20 students still lacked enthusiasm for independent study or learning to improve their speaking performance. This indicated that they required assistance, which was typically given verbally during class lectures, while the other students worked independently. In this context, we share ([Klemm, 2005](#)) perspective of the advantages of collaborative group learning. He was a professional instructor who mediated asynchronous computer-supported learning to suit all different learning styles. The process of group discussion and

communication, collaboration between groups, and the entire class with the potential for sharing learning resources, small group collaboration insightful for practicing new language further within the entire class, and media for help-seeking and solutions a few examples of how F2F interactions have facilitated these processes. Roberts (2004) asserts that observational data, field notes, and teachers' impressions demonstrate that integrating language learning with modern technologies can help students learn collaboratively, both synchronously and asynchronously. In a similar way, Atmowardoyo, Weda, and Sakkir (2020) also said that millennial learners can improve their English language skills by using information technology.

The current study also took into account the evident fact that speaking skills among students improved when teachers changed the way they formed groups based on roles. The behavior and performance of the students are also impacted by changes in group makeup. According to students' perceptions, creating groups makes sense given their commitment to developing and completing project processes. The five responsibilities in formatting are speaker, presenter, uploader, leader, and summarizer. It attempted to promote good dependency and accountability by example. Conceptually, it was about collaborative learning (Odo, Masthoff, & Beacham, 2019)). Students' speaking performances get more assured the more they engage in group projects (Butarbutar, Leba, & Sauhenda, 2022).

The current study explores several ideas, actions, and tactics that supported GBCL implementation in light of the findings from the observation checklist (Table 1). Experience has shown us that teachers always start their preparations for class activities well in advance. They felt that GBCL's efforts to motivate students to be more active were a major achievement. Then, teachers carefully evaluated whether or not the pupils understood the group topic. Teachers occasionally used their own lesson plans and course materials to do this. However, on occasion, teachers used to conduct the English lesson since they were preoccupied with other tasks and lacked the time to organize the syllabus. The teacher may also assign them to participate in a roundtable discussion and debate before presenting freely chosen themes. Students should be seated in a "U" shape to maximize involvement and make it simpler for the teacher to oversee and manage the contributions of each group member. It will be often switched out to ensure variety in personality. The documented list of grades reflects the quality of the students' speaking performances. Not to add that students believe that receiving constructive peer criticism increases their confidence. Whether the teacher graded them or they hesitated, it made a difference. Issa (2012) study, which found that task peer and self-based evaluation can foster learning skills in higher education, has supported this investigation.

4. CONCLUSION

The current study gives us important information about how English is taught as a foreign language in Indonesia and other places. We think that guided-blended collaborative learning is a new way to teach groups of students in which teachers guide or watch over students at different times and in different ways at the same time. Because of this, collaborative learning is not totally under the teachers' control, but in this situation, collaboration works best when teachers serve as guides or group controllers. During group discussions, most students were quiet and refused to participate. When teachers and students were asked about it, it turned out that teachers' control over group formation, topic choice, role assignment, and the use of technology-enhanced learning strategies and techniques helped students be more interested and confident when presenting the results of their group project. Additionally, peer evaluation and teacher management have the potential to "push" students to participate more in group projects and improve their pronunciation. When technology is added to GBCL, it means that long-term

learning is more self-directed and less reliant on teachers or other people. Because of this, technology allows for universal access to educational resources.

In addition, we urge future research to focus on the following topics: (1) guided-blended collaborative learning through true experimental and control class designs; (2) in-depth analysis with multi-case studies; (3) similar exploration regarding gender perspective; (4) an experiment for other language skills; and (5) curriculum design specifically for those who speak English as a foreign language.

REFERENCES

- Atmowardoyo, H., Weda, S., & Sakkir, G. (2020). Information technology used by millennial good English language learners in an Indonesian university to improve their English skills. *Solid State Technology, 63*(5), 9532-9547.
- Banditvilai, C. (2016). Enhancing students language skills through blended learning. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning, 14*(3), 223-232.
- Bank, C. J., & Graham, C. R. (2012). *The handbook of blended learning: Global perspectives, local designs*. San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer.
- Butarbutar, R. (2021). How does technology vocaroo improve students' speaking ability? A study from learner, teacher, and researchers's perspective. *Journal of Positive Psychology and Wellbeing, 5*(3), 1635-1640.
- Butarbutar, R. (2021b). Learner's perception of task difficulties in technology-mediated task-based language teaching. *Englisia: Journal of Language, Education, and Humanities, 9*(1), 129-144.
- Butarbutar, R., & Leba, S. M. R. (2023). Teachers' perspectives on teaching EFL speaking virtually: A case study of COVID-19 pandemic survival. *American Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, 8*(1), 46-54.
- Butarbutar, R., Leba, S. M. R., & Sauhenda, A. F. (2022). The impact of video integrated with Bloom's taxonomy on the improvement of English-speaking performance. *Journal of English Educators Society, 7*(2), 126-134. <https://doi.org/10.21070/jees.v7i2.1649>
- Crook, C. (1994). Computers and the collaborative experience of learning. In (pp. 18). London: Routledge.
- De Hei, M. S. A., Strijbos, J.-W., Sjoer, E., & Admiraal, W. (2015). Collaborative learning in higher education: Lecturers' practices and beliefs. *Research Papers in Education, 30*(2), 232-247. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2014.908407>
- Dillenbourg, P. (1999). What do you mean by collaborative learning? In P. Dillenbourg (Ed) collaborative-learning: Cognitive and computational approaches. In (pp. 1-19). Oxford: Elsevier.
- Dzemidzic Kristiansen, S., Burner, T., & Johnsen, B. H. (2019). Face-to-face promotive interaction leading to successful cooperative learning: A review study. *Cogent Education, 6*(1), 1674067. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2019.1674067>
- Goodsell, A. S. (1992). Collaborative learning: A sourcebook for higher education. In (pp. 6-29). USA: National Center on Postsecondary Teaching, Learning, and Assessment
- Issa, T. (2012). *Promoting learning skills through teamwork assessment and self/peer evaluation in higher education*. Paper presented at the In Proceedings of the IADIS International Conference on Cognition and Exploratory Learning in the Digital (CELDA 2012) IADIS Press.
- Karabinar, S., & Guler, C. Y. (2013). A review of intercultural competence from language teachers' perspective. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, 70*, 1316-1328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.01.193>
- Kitzinger, J. (2005). Focus group research: Using group dynamics. *Qualitative Research In Health Care*. In (pp. 56-70). England: Open University Press.
- Klemm, W. R. (2005). Use and misuse of technology for online, asynchronous, collaborative learning. In Computer-supported collaborative learning in higher education. In (pp. 172-200). United States of America: Idea Group Publishing (An imprint of Idea Group Inc/IGI Global).

- Liang, W. (2022). Towards a set of design principles for technology-assisted critical-thinking cultivation: A synthesis of research in English language education. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 47, 101203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2022.101203>
- Lin, L. (2015). The collaborative learning research project: From theory to practice. In Investigating Chinese, HE EFL classrooms. In (pp. 43-69). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer.
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2015). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco, CA: John Wiley & Sons.
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldaña, J. (2018). *Qualitative data analysis: A methods sourcebook*. In (3rd ed., pp. 116-148). United States of America: Sage Publications.
- Muswazi, M., & Nhamo, E. (2013). Note taking: A lesson for novice qualitative researchers. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 2(3), 13-17. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-0231317>
- Nur, S., & Butarbutar, R. (2022a). *Youtube-based collaborative learning and speaking self-efficacy: A case study in A Rural Area*. Paper presented at the The International Research Conference of Universitas Maarif Hasyim.
- Nur, S., & Butarbutar, R. (2022b). A narrative inquiry of students' self-directed learning in EFL speaking class through youtube. *Celebes Journal of Language Studies*, 2(2), 193-206.
- Odo, C., Masthoff, J., & Beacham, N. (2019). *Group formation for collaborative learning*. Paper presented at the In International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Education, Springer, Cham.
- Phillippi, J., & Lauderdale, J. (2018). A guide to field notes for qualitative research: Context and conversation. *Qualitative Health Research*, 28(3), 381-388. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732317697102>
- Prior, L. (2016). Using documents in social research, *Qualitative research*. In (pp. 171-185). London: Sage.
- Roberts, T. S. (2004). *Online collaborative learning: Theory and practice*. In (pp. 336). Australia: Central Queensland University.
- Seidman, I. (2006). *Interviewing as qualitative research: A guide for researchers in education and the social sciences* (3rd ed.). New York and London: Teachers College Press.
- Stockdale, A. (2002). *Tools for digital audio recording in qualitative research, social research update* (Vol. 38). United Kingdom: University of Surrey.
- Tauchid, A., Saleh, M., Hartono, R., & Mujiyanto, J. (2022). English as an international language (EIL) views in Indonesia and Japan: A survey research. *Heliyon*, 8(10), e10785. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10785>
- Thornbury, S. (2016). *Communicative language teaching in theory and practice*. In *The Routledge handbook of English language teaching*. London: Routledge.
- Thorne, K. (2003). *Blended learning: How to integrate online & traditional learning*. London, UK: Kogan Page Publishers.
- Wang, Y. C. (2020). *Promoting English listening and speaking ability by computer-supported collaborative learning*. Paper presented at the In Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on E-Education, E-Business, E-Management, and E-Learning.
- Yin, R. K. (2003). *Applications of case study research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Yin, R. K. (2006). Mixed methods research: Are the methods genuinely integrated or merely parallel. *Research in the Schools*, 13(1), 41-47.
- Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods* (4th ed.). Los Angeles: Sage Publications.
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications* (6th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Online Science Publishing is not responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability, etc. caused in relation to/arising out of the use of the content. Any queries should be directed to the corresponding author of the article.